

PARADIGMS FOR SOLVING PROBLEMS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article presents a sociological analysis of reforms in the preschool education system, problems in their implementation, and paradigms of their elimination. The analysis was carried out based on the "Concept of developing the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" and the scientific views of pedagogic scientists.*

Keywords: *paradigm, social, education, person-oriented education, pedagogue, skill, knowledge, quality, efficiency.*

In Uzbekistan, on the one hand, due to reforms, on the other hand, scientific and technical progress, and on the third hand, the development of society, new approaches and solutions to development are reflected in the socio-economic and political behavior of people. There is a need for critical analytical research as well as scientific research related to all areas of modernized society, recommendations and predictions that ensure social development. Realization of such a need, daily life, forms of interaction between people require people to be proactive. The development of such activity falls directly on the responsibility of the education system. Because education inspires children to achieve high results and encourages them to make wise use of all opportunities in life, to reveal their individual abilities, to actively and constructively solve the achievements and shortcomings in the field of socio-economic, educational and cultural development, creativity and initiative. Studying and researching the existing problems and the need to eliminate them in the education of people who can show is one of the urgent issues of educational sociology.

Educational sociology theorist D.E.Durkheim views education as a social institution that changes its nature "throughout the ages and in all known societies" and emphasizes the importance of education in the process of teaching moral values as the foundation of society. According to D.E.Durkheim, education is a continuous process of socialization, during which social culture and social order are formed in society. Because realizing society's need for an active, creative, initiative subject is not only to introduce young people to universal or national values, principles, rules and regulations, but also to encourage them to independently strive and search for determining their inclinations, only by forming them as individuals, it will be possible to ensure the social culture and social order that D.E.Durkheim emphasized. This allows us to further develop the social experience of the previous generations and pass it on to the next generations, consistently and systematically implement reforms in the education system, improve the consciousness and behavior of children in accordance with the requirements of the times, and fill the essence of the modern education process. In the harmony of traditionalism and modernity, children are not only an object of influence. Perhaps it requires acceptance as a subject. This attitude creates the basis for maintaining the child's personality, and does not fully ensure children's effective adaptation to society and their integration into social life. Its quality implementation depends on the realistic implementation of reforms in the field of preschool education. However, it is reasonable to

determine the quality, content and direction of preschool education and upbringing in our country, to raise the question of how well this level corresponds to the requirements of the time. Because in order to ensure the quality of preschool education, first of all, adults should abandon their old concepts about childhood and children's world, they should have a clear idea about the essence of children's development, who and what kind of person they should be in the future. However, the fact that children of preschool age are still viewed as playboys shows how important the problem of analyzing the specific characteristics of children's development and determining the laws of this process is. Providing education to young children at the professional-pedagogical level in preschool education, which is the first stage of education, based on state requirements and standards, serves to form the main qualities of human personality in the first years of a child's life. Because it is from this period that the child's cognitive abilities, physical, social, moral, intellectual and communicative spheres are quickly mastered. Therefore, the educational process in pre-school education organizations carried out during this period embodies activity-based and integrative approaches to the formation of a child's personality. In particular, when preparing children for school, work is done with the task of improving reading and calculation skills, in which special importance is attached to the development of their fine motor skills and oral speech. That is, to the social side of education, which is related to the development of effective communication skills in children, cooperation, self-development, the ability to regulate one's own situation, etc. attention is required. If we take into account that education, including preschool education, as stated by Durkheim, is a social institution that changes its nature in accordance with the requirements of the time, it is necessary to consider the field of education as a process that is consciously controlled and based on special knowledge as a real phenomenon. Another famous scientist A.B.Merenkov, the essence and purpose of the preschool period of a person's life is to develop the main mechanisms, methods, means of introducing adults to the world, to ensure the child's effective integration into society due to the acquisition of basic values and norms, and his interaction with the microenvironment. emphasizes the need to determine the relationship, to ensure the mastery of the norms of joint life activities of people, as well as to master the methods of self-development in old age.

In the implementation of the above paradigms, it is necessary to focus on the problem of teaching children to think independently and logically, creating a developmental environment that matches the requirements of the state educational standard for preschool education, as well as the pedagogue-educator implementing the national program. emphasizes that he should develop the basic competencies. These competencies include ensuring emotional well-being, supporting children's individuality and initiative, establishing rules of behavior and interactions in various situations, forming developmental education focused on the zone of proximal development of each child, It includes interaction with parents on educational issues.

Reforms in the preschool education system and the integration of multi-subject content in the innovative space increase the need to implement integration and differential education in the field. Because it is important to introduce new content to the system of personnel training and retraining on issues of personality formation of preschool children. It is necessary to solve the issues of integration of educational areas, complex thematic planning, monitoring activities, etc. in the process of organizing training courses for pedagogical personnel, theoretical seminars and practical training. Therefore, one of the priority tasks is to develop the potential of personnel in the preschool education system, to reform the pedagogical activity of the pedagogue-educator in

accordance with the very serious demands placed on him today, first of all, to develop communication techniques taking into account the individual characteristics of each child. requires mastery. It should be noted that the requirements for the professional competence of the pedagogue-educator in the preschool education system are constantly changing. Because, as a result of reforms in the field and changes in society, the professional requirements for their profession also change. In the concept of development of the system of preschool education in Uzbekistan until 2030, the objectives, tasks, priority directions, stages of the development of preschool education in the medium and long-term perspective are defined and the way to the development of the field of preschool education organizing the educational process of preschool children through the development of focused programs and comprehensive measures, in which the main goal is to focus on the quality of education. As indicators of the effectiveness of education of children of preschool age, the level of development of the child's initial competencies is available, and it can be observed that they are aimed at developing the ability to solve life problems, and that integrative personal characteristics are promoted.

In the concept, it is emphasized to follow the principle of creating an environment of active development in pre-school educational organizations, taking into account that the priority view of the educational process is a feature of the educational and disciplined pedagogical paradigm. Because such an approach to the educational process is often a reproductive approach, it also covers the issues of increasing the information volume of primary knowledge and stimulating the cognitive activities of preschool children, developing independence, initiative, determination and creativity. It is necessary to pay attention to the development of educational games. As a result of the lack of pedagogical skills, many pedagogues working in the field use “general education school” technologies and are overly obsessed with different forms of teaching. However, in activating the intellectual and social development of preschool children, working based on state standards and requirements and program requirements takes an important place. Taking into account that the main content of the modern preschool education system is aimed at expressing the priority areas of children's development, it is appropriate to implement multi-disciplinary hyper-character pedagogical activities that serve to develop the intellectual activity of children in the process of educational game activities. All the above-mentioned didactic materials should serve to ensure comprehensive development of children of preschool age in a holistic way with their power of providing information and language features. F. Kadirova, Sh. Toshpulatova, N. Kayumova, N. Azamova “believe that activity plays a leading role in the development of a child, therefore, in the preschool educational organization and in the family, the child's life should be created and enriched with various activities. boorish, they express the view that new knowledge is achieved by the development of independence of assimilation of skills”.

These views are directly related to A.V. Zaporozhets considers the development of children of preschool age as enrichment, and such development includes filling the pedagogical process in the preschool educational organization with the most important forms and methods of activity (games, communication of the child with adults and peers, children's work, visual art) is consistent with his thoughts. A.V. Zaporozhets showed that "enrichment" allows maintaining and strengthening the child's physical and mental health, ensures its normal development and preserves the joy of childhood. In recent years, a number of democratic changes in society have had little impact on education, the most effective paradigm of child-centered education was developed and put into practice in solving problems in preschool education. . In turn, the

effectiveness of education shapes the child's social image through self-awareness. Taking this into account, the supporters of the person-oriented pedagogical paradigm deny the frontal approach to the education of children in preschool educational institutions.

Achieving educational efficiency requires, first of all, self-development of pedagogues-educators, working on themselves and regularly improving their knowledge. Involvement of the child in educational game activities should awaken the child's internal need for knowledge in order to develop cognitive competence. For this purpose, the pedagogue-educator of the preschool educational organization should be able to clearly set the goals in the activity of the educational game, choose the right educational technologies based on the content and tasks of the subject, and create information based on the basic character of the society. and is required to have the skills to transfer it. The main goal of this approach is to form a system of qualities necessary for mastering educational activities in a preschool child - curiosity, initiative, independence, manifestation of the child's creative self, etc.

S.A. Kozlova, one of the supporters of the person-oriented pedagogical paradigm. T.A. Kulikova specifically emphasizes that its implementation "in no case implies the cancellation of systematic teaching and upbringing of children, carrying out systematic pedagogical work with them." Only the narrow interpretation of the term "preschool preparation" is rejected. It is related to the priority solution of educational problems. From the point of view of a person-oriented approach, the main goal of school preparation is the formation of a system of qualities necessary for the mastering of educational activities in a preschool child - curiosity, initiative, independence, self-discipline, the child's creative self-expression, etc. . Pedagogical communication methods require consideration of the child's interests, feelings, while respecting the child's "I". In this process, the actions of the pedagogue-educator are based on the interests of the child and the prospects of his further development as a full-fledged member of society. In turn, when self-education and development of a pedagogue-educator is encouraged by intellectual culture as a means of ensuring the emotional and intellectual development of preschool children and educational efficiency, spiritual values for professional activity helps to master consciously and purposefully.

In this article, we looked at the activity of the school education system through the prism of reforms, and expressed our views on the problems in the field and some pedagogical paradigms for their elimination.

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